

Sydney Startup Hub's Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2022 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws on prior research and engagement projects to visualise entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which teams of students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals to advance the ecosystem.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

General Methodology

In partnership with Investment NSW (e.g., Sydney Startup Hub) and Spark Festival, the cohort of ~45 students was given the option to focus on Sydney CBD, Western Sydney, or Nationally. Additionally, one team was based overseas and was free to choose an international city to navigate.

The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,³ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE).

In addition to learning about ecosystems, teams engaged with ecosystems in authentic and immersive learning experiences. Stakeholder types and specific stakeholders in the ecosystem were identified based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. Insights about the ecosystem were generated by analysing desktop reports and media interviews involved those stakeholders. Where possible, teams conducted their own interviews of key stakeholders, including asking them about the ecosystem's history, evolution and critical events, and their vision for how it may evolve further. By synthesising such reports and interviews from multiple stakeholders, teams developed a composite story of the ecosystem's evolution, visualised its current state and identified specific opportunities for change. These reports present this analysis of the ecosystems' evolution as well as the team's proposal for specific interventions by which to intentionally advance the ecosystem in a specific direction.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

Contents

Foreword	3
General Methodology	3
Acknowledgements	3
1 Evolution of the Ecosystem	5
2 Leverage Proposal	8
2.1 Envisioning the Future	8
2.2 Leverage Proposal 1	8
2.3 Leverage Proposal 2	9
2.4 Valuing the proposed levers	9
References	11

1 Evolution of the Ecosystem

Sydney Startup Hub (SSH) was founded in 2017 and finalised and realised in 2018 to the public. In under three years, SSH has assisted in establishing Sydney and New south wales as an ideal location for entrepreneurs to explore their ideas and execute innovation. It is found that nearly half of all 'Australian' startups are "coconceptualized, developed, and launched in the hub." (Startupoasis, 2021). It is also stated that the hub has created more than 1,000 jobs and brought in a net revenue of over 200million dollars in investments.

The hub itself is home to around 2,500 residents (Startup daily, 2022) and thousands more when you factor in the community and event spaces. It is located on 11 York Street, Sydney, which is the heart of the city's CBD geographically. With fintech companies booming and becoming one of the biggest industries in the world today and the rise and reign of Silicon Valley, governments have been trying to influence and recreate such innovation in how Sydney start-up hub as an organisation and location has been created.

Some successful Sydney startups within the space –

1. Canva

Canva is a popular graphic design platform. Designers (and non-designers) use it to create professional-looking social media posts and graphics, presentations, business posters and cards, logos, videos, and other related design materials. It allows users access to licence-free images and features a drag-and-drop designing tool and templates. Total funding as of this writing is \$301 Million.

2. Spaceship

Spaceship is a financial services startup in Australia. It is focused on providing investment opportunities to younger generations. It is based on an online app where users can find diverse options for wealth-building and investment plans. It has completed a total funding of 301 Million Australian Dollars.

3. Judo Bank

Judo Bank is a Start-up in the financial services sector and is considered to be a unicorn Company. The business goal and purpose is to provide world-class financial solutions to SMEs. Its online platform provides loans and other SME needs. Judo Bank is managed by relationship managers. Total funding as of this writing is \$1.7 billion.

Australia's top startups have several things in common:

- They're able and willing to innovate
- They plan thoroughly
- They launch and execute their products in a timely manner.

These unicorn start-ups are the reason in which Sydney Start-up Hub was needed and once in full operation could be part of successful companies that spread throughout the global fintech industry.

The main objectives of the hub are to:

- Act as the support system for NSW's new jobs creation projects
- Improve and encourage startup diversity by embracing regional NSW industries and non-ICT businesses
- Grow, develop, and strengthen the startup ecosystem in Sydney

Figure 1: Sydney Startup Hub's Ecosystem Map

This visual of the ecosystem map represents Sydney Startup Hub as the centre of the entrepreneurial ecosystem which interconnected and interlinked with the society, education, incubators, technology companies and the government. Based on our research findings in the previous assessment, we are able to locate these key stakeholders that support each element of Sydney Startup Hub. The ecosystem map shows six important stakeholders, each of which are essential to the ecosystem's growth.

Government support has helped Sydney Startup Hub grow into a thriving functioning environment. For example, Investment NSW, Transport NSW, and City of Sydney. These stakeholders are a part of the entrepreneurial ecosystem because the ecosystem itself relates to the Sydney city CBD area. They hugely influence and link the financial aspect to the ecosystem. Without the influence of the people and the government in city Sydney, the ecosystem would not be complete with enforceable laws and regulations. Technology impacts a lot on the emergence of the ecosystem. Especially with the upcoming project of the tech central and the future visualisation of Syd-con Valley. Technology is the key playing factor that we would discuss furthermore in the Sydney entrepreneurial ecosystem. The progress and success of the ecosystem relies on technology. Technology also relates to education and incubators as they produce innovative technologies that support the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

There are key elements related to education as part of the ecosystem. Education brings a lot of impact to the ecosystem with the availability of knowledge from universities, emerging startups, Ted talks, etc. University graduates, lecturers, and professors have a lot of potential to contribute to the growth of the entrepreneurial environment. Education system provides a lot as the ecosystem develops, it helps with the knowledge element and emergence of new incubators practised by universities. Moreover, focus groups and collaborative areas with UTS startups, TEDEd talks, and many more will support the ecosystem. We would like to focus on the people element in the ecosystem as the key stakeholder because it is the key that drives the ecosystem itself. Built, operated, and run for the people in the ecosystem. This could be influencers, knowledgeable people, government personnel, environmentalists for sustainability, and many more.

The financial factor is essential to the entrepreneurial ecosystem by looking out for investors overseas and within the Sydney city area. Making an awareness that there is a potential in Sydney for innovation and technological advancement and development. These financial factors include financial firms, angel investors, business or startup investors, etc.

Incubators, the home of many startups, is an essential stakeholder in the ecosystem. Incubators provided new emerging startups that supported the entrepreneurial ecosystem to collaborate innovative ideas, advance technology, sustainability ideas, and provide for the future.

We first start concentrating on the Government section regarding how they link together. Minister (People) and City of Sydney (Gov) are related to each other as there are different types of ministers in the City of Sydney that can function with their own rules and regulations created by the state government. To ensure they are involved in the decision-making process, they frequently engage with their communities to get the entrepreneurs, other stakeholders and local parties (City of Sydney, n.d.).

Although both components are in the same sector, the City of Sydney provides Transport NSW details. Transport NSW established public transport such as light rails, taxis, buses and airport trains, allowing people to have easier access to go from one place to another. Furthermore, employees, tourists and locals can enjoy secure streets daily (City of Sydney, n.d.).

Invest NSW (Gov) and Transport NSW (Gov): Investment NSW contributes to and supports Transport NSW as they invest in transport plans. Big things are expected for the strategy of NSW Government Future Transport 2056. To guarantee they can accomplish their goals, the NSW Government is implementing changes to the NSW and Sydney transportation networks. As SSH focuses on the future of transport innovation, the NSW Government is trying to assist the companies that will help shape the transportation future in their region. Support companies include:

- A Future Transport 2056 Strategy: concentrates on six main results for the state's future mobility. This strategy aims to enhance the NSW environment, communities and economy.
- A Transport and Logistics Knowledge Hub: ensure best protocols are maintained and develop industry connections.
- A Transport Digital Incubator and Innovation Challenges: strives to link and create real-time details, provide demand reactive services and meet people's needs (NSW Government, n.d.).

The Business of Entrepreneurship is a BDO program for early-stage and booming industries in NSW that concentrates on financial education and company growth. Sydney Startup Hub, Investment of NSW group, and BDO have created a partnership to provide financial masterclass studies for scaleups and startups aiming to advance their business. Furthermore, they provide their Business of Entrepreneurship Programs to scaleups and startups in NSW's country and significant cities free of charge (BDO Australia, n.d.).

Next, we looked at the education section. UTS startups, University and Compass IoT are linked together since most universities encourage students to do startup business and guide them on how to build their own startup business. Universities such as Sydney Knowledge Hub and UTS Startup offer a creative ecosystem and collaboration space to enhance commercialization results (The University of Sydney, n.d.). For instance, Compass IoT wins UTS Startup of the Year. They are linked with technology sectors since they utilise connected vehicles to gather information on g-force, volume, safety and speed across the transportation system. Moreover, they give transport providers access to historical and current data on a city's operations (UTS, n.d.).

Most UTS students create startups based on the technology sector as most develop mobile apps that can help people increase their productivity and benefit society. Tech startups based on UTS are Myrrha, Titan Biomechanics, Swan Energy, MakeShuffleShift, and others (UTS, n.d.). Ted talk, incubators and influencers are related to each other as Ted talk has invited many guest speakers who have their startup businesses and can explain how they create their startup businesses from scratch. Hence, the audience feels motivated and inspired by their creative and innovative ideas on doing a startup business. Furthermore, they provide the audience with an essential manual for starting a business (TED, 2019.).

Sydney Startup Hub has many incubators such as Fishburners, Optus, Stone & Chalk, Tank Stream Labs and Microsoft reactors. Incubators and technology are related as most of them are tech startups and create a tech community that can benefit the Sydney Startup Hub. Most incubators want to develop co-working spaces that concentrate on technology, enhance Australian technology, and improve the technology ecosystem to promote innovation in recent technologies for beneficial effects (Stone & Chalk, n.d.).

Spaceship finance is linked with fintech companies as it has mobile apps and software to enhance and optimise conventional financial methods for customers and companies. Its mobile app enables customers to invest and keep track of their investments as they concentrate on the future. By adding one or more accounts, they can spread their investment and monitor their return, unit price and balance in their single account (Spaceship, n.d.). Hence, Spaceship financial companies apply technology to change and improve financial services for companies or customers (Columbia Engineering Bootcamps, n.d.).

2 Leverage Proposal

2.1 Envisioning the Future

In ten years, we envision Sydney Startup Hub as the heart of a flourishing society. A space where startups are able to cultivate product fitness, as well as develop into potential unicorns. Within our definition, we envision a geographical location that accommodates and attracts the talent and culture that allows for innovation to thrive. A space with a willingness to take that risk into entrepreneurship and the sharing of ideas.

The gaps in our current ecosystem, at its core, is the lack of interconnectivity between the stakeholders within the ecosystem. Our ecosystem map highlights the relationships between different areas of the ecosystem, however with field research and talking to founders of Sydney-based startups, there seems to be a lot of untapped potential in the relationships between the parties involved. Additionally, the physical ecosystem that's attractive and therefore allowing for SSH to become the heart of a flourishing society. In stating this, there are opportunities available to address the gaps within the space. The ecosystem has the potential to attract investors and venture capitalists - we have the opportunity now to bring them in and present all the potential SSH and its tenants have. Furthermore, existing infrastructure can be upcycled to generate hubs like 'Greenhouse' in Sydney's CBD, or 'Station F' in Paris.

2.2 Leverage Proposal 1

This leverage proposal is developed as a response to two observed trends,

1. The increasing number of startups within the ecosystem - there are 333 startups working out of SSH's physical space, with a further 3,375 working from regional areas (Carol Friel, SSH powerpoint)
2. Innovation and entrepreneurship holds a multitude of economic benefits - SSH alone recorded a creation of 6,000 jobs (Carol Friel, SSH powerpoint). As a result, governmental investment within the space is growing - SSH having received \$35M in capital funding (Investment NSW), and other precinct investments such as TechCentral

The above trends reveal a gap within the ecosystem - limited resources in the form of funding and capital, leading to increased competition within the market. Ben Kennedy from Gecko earlier in the year had ventured out to San Francisco, and through primary research, Ben speaks of the lack of resources and aid that the Sydney ecosystem seems to be lacking in. Additionally, he states, 'I'd like to see more VCs that used to be operators and less coaches giving advice about things they haven't ever done themselves'. As a result, our leverage proposal is to bring in more 'operational' based VCs who are willing and able to take the investment and risk on Australian startups with high-growth potential.

Providing incentives and attracting more venture capital individuals and organisations within the next three years provides the ecosystem with foundational structures and figures that are external to governmental aid. Organisations such as BlackBird Ventures, or AirTree Ventures already exist within the space, and by bringing in Silicon Valley level venture capital organisations, such as Accel Partners and Corner Ventures, the Sydney Startup Hub ecosystem is able to have access to supportive networks. The introduction of new venture capitalists within the space would provide the ecosystem with a 'backbone support' (Kania and Kramer, 2011). Through a partnership with Sydney Startup Hub and the consequential campaign to initiate the program, the new venture capital companies into the ecosystem would 'serve as the backbone for the entire intuitive and coordinated participating organisations and agencies' (Kauffman Foundation).

With reference to Meadow's Levers for Systems (1997), the introduction of more operational VCs into the Sydney Startup Hub's ecosystem categories as 'material stocks and flows' and 'the power of self-organisation'. By committing to the following change within the ecosystem, we're able to strengthen the connections between each individual or organisation within the space. Furthermore, equipping beginner stage 'high-growth' startups with effective and results driven networks allows for the ecosystem to evolve. This means evolving from a 'nascent ecosystem' to one that is 'resilient' (Spigel and Harrison, 2017) as more 'significant new resources [are] attracted to the ecosystem'.

2.3 Leverage Proposal 2

With Sydney growing faster by the day, it is of huge importance that the city has proper plans and management strategies to ensure it has potential to grow sustainably. Urban Planning and Development is a valuable tool to have when discussing current gaps and opportunities for the Sydney Startup Hub ecosystem. The current benefits of the startup hub scene in Sydney has many economic implications, with quality planning, places can add more to public value and empower the community (PIA 2017). Patrick Fensham is a key activator that has experience in both issues we are going to discuss, developing and planning in all states of Australia.

By enabling proper planning, it is capable to build hubs that are not only labelled as innovative and collaborative but encapsulate its meaning. At times you are only what your environment allows you to be. The first of two concepts we've recognised in this area are as follows:

- Building village-like hubs and repurposing unused urban land spaces that are interconnected can make a significant contribution to the city's livability which will increasingly underpin its global competitiveness (Patrick Fensham, 2008).
- Combating unaffordable housing and transport hubs (Patrick Fensham 2016).

In order to add opportunity and close gaps to the current ecosystem, these two ideas are best appropriate as they provide a benefit to Sydney residents which could have major implications for those looking to build and work for startups in Sydney. When comparing the best startup scenes globally, it is "their economies that are underpinned by the creativity and constant innovation that occurs where skilled people mix in social, business and cultural activities" (Patrick Fensham 2008, p.22). Here is a closer look at each concept.

Sydney is full of small suburbs that each build on their existing cultures and activities. Some areas are at the core of the startup scene which could add to the ecosystem. Places like Darlinghurst, Camperdown and Surry Hills to name a few, are constantly strengthened by their small businesses that stand out individually which helps to foster local economies. The idea that helping to build more innovative villages like these can further create opportunity for those in different areas, rather than just on the outskirts of the CBD. By planning and repurposing old land spaces like Carriage Works and White Bay Power Station, the Sydney startup ecosystem would greatly benefit from such works. With projects like these, innovation and entrepreneurship would help to create.

In conjunction with the above, building affordable housing within walking distance of key transport hubs can greatly reduce the effect of communities becoming alienated. This could greatly benefit Sydney's startup ecosystem in the sense that people of lower incomes who rent would be provided opportunities they may have only been afforded with a car or other transportation. This is further supported by John Engler, CEO of Shelter NSW (2022) where people living outside the wealthy Sydney bubble have to travel long distances – often out of regular work hours – to their places of employment.

2.4 Valuing the proposed levers

Essentially, as a proposal we have worked on areas that would best draw attention to Sydney as a startup/entrepreneurial ecosystem. By drawing attention to its potential and weaknesses we were better able to show how people from Silicon Valley, Singapore and France etc could consider starting up and working in Sydney. The value of this can help create a more productive and invested community within the startup hub ecosystem and further future capabilities. The levers were drawn up not only to bring easier access for those outside Sydney CBD bounds but also for innovators outside of Australia. Further, as an ecosystem that lacks the collaborative effort, the proposals sought to bring more entrepreneurial and connected feeling to infrastructure built. Hubs will draw all manner of people willing to help each other and make use of their previous experiences.

In regards to our activators, starting with Patrick Fensham. Patrick has had a unique career in that he's built foundational levels of planning in many states. He's been awarded for his works on Victoria's regional land use plans in 2018 & 2019 and was lead consultant for Australia's 2030 Sustainable Sydney report. From a more personal, sympathetic angle, he's notably focused on addressing social disadvantage in urban and regional contexts. As our leverage proposal is based on ensuring the socially disadvantaged have access to the startup hub and transforming Sydney's unused spaces for innovative purposes, one could only ask why Patrick wouldn't want to be concerned with building Sydney's startup spaces to make entrepreneurial minds from all over easily accessible. This proposal will generate future jobs, increase Australia's startup scene and make some hard choices a lot less stressful.

The other potential activators in leveraging this opportunity are the domestic and overseas venture capital organisations and individuals. In appealing to these groups, we're able to optimise results and allow for the

achievement of a flourishing ecosystem. Research has shown from asking various stakeholders and friends that work in Silicon Valley that there are more relationships that are developed and ongoing within the startup space, compared to Sydney. Sydney's key areas for improvement would be that as it is still in early stages and there needs to be more dialogue and appeal for investors to start bringing in money. Sydney's Mayor, Clover Moore has highlighted that "One of the biggest challenges start-up businesses in Sydney face is attracting serious financial support – for businesses with the potential to become global players, that can mean funding in the vicinity of \$100,000 to a million dollars," Cr Moore said. "The people with that kind of money to spend are putting it into property, mining and exploration. "We need to start redirecting some of that money into our local talent, as well as encouraging the government to look at tax incentives, so we can help innovative small businesses grow into the mid-sized or larger businesses of Sydney's future." (Sharma 2012). It is these kinds of reasons that we targeted venture capitalists, this is not always a government issue. The development of the startup ecosystem is key to bringing forth more trust and collaboration in this sense.

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